

A Study of Attitude towards E-Teaching among Govt-Aided School Teachers

Dr.K.Usharani

Assistant Professor, Department Of Physical Science
Cms College of Education, Coimbatore

Corresponding author- Dr.K.Usharani

Email: usharanijr@gmail.com

Abstract

Technological advancements have changed many traditional methods of teaching-learning process into a more dynamic and forward looking concept. E-teaching is one such new concept in the field of education. In order to enhance the success of e-teaching, teachers must fulfill several non-trivial conditions. Hence it is necessary for a teacher to have certain level of proficiency in the concept of e-teaching. The present study was under taken to investigate the study on attitude towards e- teaching among Government Aided school teachers. The sample of the study comprised of 150 Government Aided school teachers who were selected through random sampling technique to measure attitude towards e- teaching. A questionnaire on attitude towards e- teaching with seven factors i) Technology ii) e-teaching iii) Training and development iv) Learning environment v) heterogeneous group vi) Student management vii) Infrastructure was developed by the investigator. The findings of the study revealed that i) There is no significant difference in the attitude towards e-teaching between the Government Aided school teachers based on their qualification. ii) There is a significant difference in the attitude towards e-teaching between the arts and science Government Aided school teachers for the factors technology, student management, training and development iii) There is no significance difference in the attitude towards e-teaching between rural Government Aided school teachers and urban Govt.Aided school teachers. The present study has revealed that there is a high level of attitude towards e-teaching among Government Aided school teachers

Introduction

Arrival of computer and internet in the field of education has changed the procedure and pattern of education. Now education knocks at the door of student or learners. Technological advancements have changed many traditional methods of teaching-learning process into a more dynamic and forward looking concept. Thus e-teaching is one such new concept in the field of education. In order to enhance the success of e-teaching teachers must fulfill several non-trivial conditions. Hence it is necessary for a teacher to have certain level of proficiency in the concept of e-teaching. In the present study the researcher has made an attempt to study the attitude of Government teachers towards e-teaching. During the past few years a revolution has taken place in the teaching learning process of education. Technology plays a significant role on imparting education at all level i.e., from primary to higher. Now a day the alphabet “e” being attached has become more popular with relative ease, “e” has been attached to activities like real estate, retailing banking, entertainment and now in education. The “e” transfer electronic and it relates to the use of internet to undertake wide range of activities. As we become more familiar with a language of the internet refined how it pervades our daily lives in the dot.com age. Educators are now beginning to hear terms like e-teaching, e-learning and e-education as it subtly becomes a part of our regular vocabulary.

Significance of the study

The explosions of ICT development have a great impact in the application of different technology and electronic media in the teaching learning process with the advancement of science

and technology. Teachers have started to supplement their teaching with new technologies. A wide range of technologies are available today for the teachers, through which they could impart instruction to students. Both central and State government have formulated many schemes and programmed to popularize the utilization of ICT among school teachers. As a result of this concept like smart class room, virtual classroom, digital library, electronic community and multimedia learning are gaining the attention of teaching community. All these innovations in the field of educational technology have contributed to the birth of a new concept called e- teaching. The purpose of the study is to analyze the attitude towards e-teaching among government Aided school teachers.

Objectives:

To study the attitude towards e-teaching among Government Aided school teachers.

Hypothesis:

1. There will be a significant mean score difference in the attitude towards e-teaching between the rural and urban Government Aided school teachers.
2. There will be a significant mean score difference in attitude towards e-teaching between the UG and PG Government Aided school teachers.
3. There will be a significant mean score difference in attitude towards e-teaching between Arts and Science Government Aided school teachers.

Methodology: Survey method was adopted to collect the data. Attitude towards e- teaching schedule was prepared by investigator under the

seven factors technology, e-teaching, training and development, learning environment, heterogeneous group, student management and infrastructure. 150 government aided school teachers were used as samples to collect the data. The obtained data were subjected to necessary statistical computation.

Statistical Techniques:

Hypothesis-1

There will be a significant mean score difference in attitude towards e-teaching between the rural and urban Government aided schoolteachers.

**Table 0.1 shows the mean score difference between the rural and urban:
 Government aided school teachers**

Factors	Variable (LOCALITY)	N	M	SD	df	't'	LS
Technology	RURAL	52	19.83	2.833	148	0.23	NS
	URBAN	98	19.71	2.781			
E teaching	RURAL	52	20.02	3.058	148	1.43	NS
	URBAN	98	20.77	3.011			
Training and development	RURAL	52	21.35	3.307	148	0.25	NS
	URBAN	98	21.20	3.162			
Learning environment	RURAL	52	20.21	3.310	148	0.01	NS
	URBAN	98	20.20	3.146			
Heterogeneous group	RURAL	52	20.33	3.417	148	0.39	NS
	URBAN	98	20.11	2.991			
Student management	RURAL	52	17.42	2.118	148	2.24	S
	URBAN	98	16.61	2.104			
Infrastructure	RURAL	52	21.06	2.906	148	0.34	NS
	URBAN	98	20.89	2.802			

*NS Not Significant at 0.05 level, *S Significant at 0.05 level, *LS Level of Significance

Accounting to the table t-value is not statistically significant at 0.05 levels for all the factors except student management. Hence the hypothesis is rejected for all the factors except student

Thus the collected data were screened and scrutinized by the investigator. After screening ,the data were analyzed using descriptive statistics (mean, standard deviation) and the test of significance t-test were employed for testing the hypotheses to arrive the meaningful conclusion.

management and it can be concluded that the locality difference of the Government aided school teachers does not influence their attitude towards e-teaching.

Hypothesis-2 : There will be a significant mean score difference in attitude towards e- teaching between the UG and PG Government aided school teachers

Table 0.2 shows the mean score difference between the UG and PG: Government aided school teachers

Factors	Variables Qualification	N	M	SD	df	't'	LS
Technology	UG	70	20.06	2.53	148	1.25	NS
	PG	80	19.49	2.98			
E teaching	UG	70	20.36	2.99	148	0.56	NS
	PG	80	20.64	3.08			
Training and development	UG	70	20.84	3.63	148	1.47	NS
	PG	80	21.61	2.74			
Learning and Environment	UG	70	20.29	3.47	148	0.28	NS
	PG	80	20.14	2.94			
Heterogeneous Group	UG	70	20.54	3.22	148	1.30	NS
	PG	80	19.88	3.04			
Student Management	UG	70	17.00	2.25	148	0.57	NS
	PG	80	16.80	2.04			
Infrastructure	UG	70	20.77	2.92	148	0.70	NS
	PG	80	21.10	2.75			

*NS- Not Significant at 0.05 level, *LS Level of Significance

According to the table the t-value is not statistically significant at 0.05 level for all the factors. Hence the hypothesis is rejected and it can be concluded that

the Government aided school teachers qualification does not influence their attitude towards e-teaching.

Hypothesis-3

There will be a significant mean score difference in attitude towards e-teaching between the Arts and Science Government aided school teachers.

Table 0.2 shows the mean score difference between the Arts and Science Government aided school teachers

Factors	Variables Arts and Science	N	M	SD	df	't'	LS
Technology	ARTS	86	19.24	2.902	148	2.64	S
	SCIENCE	64	20.44	2.494			
E-teaching	ARTS	86	20.27	2.867	148	1.11	NS
	SCIENCE	64	20.83	3.249			
Training and Development	ARTS	86	20.62	3.529	148	2.89	S
	SCIENCE	64	22.11	2.482			
Learning environment	ARTS	86	20.03	3.070	148	0.76	NS
	SCIENCE	64	20.44	3.361			
Heterogeneous group	ARTS	86	20.12	3.175	148	0.31	NS
	SCIENCE	64	20.28	3.104			
Student Management	ARTS	86	16.58	2.193	148	2.09	S
	SCIENCE	64	17.31	1.999			
infrastructure	ARTS	86	20.59	2.758	148	1.78	NS
	SCIENCE	64	21.42	2.877			

*NS- Not Significant at 0.05 levels, *S- Significant at 0.05 levels, *LS Level of Significance

According to the table the t-value for the factors like technology, student management training and development is statistically significant at 0.05 level. Hence the hypothesis is accepted. The remaining factors like e-teaching, learning environment, heterogeneous group, infrastructure is not statistically significant at 0.05 level. Further it can be concluded that, the variable art stream and science stream Government aided school teacher's influence the factors technology, student management, training and development.

Findings of the study:

- There is no significant difference in attitude towards e-teaching between the rural and urban government aided school teachers except the factor student management.
- There is no significant difference in attitude towards e-teaching between UG and PG government aided school teachers.
- There is significant difference in attitude towards e-teaching between the arts and science government aided school teacher only for the factors technology, student management, training and development.

Conclusion of the study:

- The present study has revealed the fact that there is high level of attitude towards e-Teaching among government aided school teachers for the factors technology and student management. Hence the concept e-teaching should be included in the school education system.

One of the major benefits of e-teaching is saving time and money.

Rain or shine, the students do not have to leave their comfortable homes to receive tutoring.

Student can avail tutoring from any place where they have internet access, being it a school or public libraries. They can have a session at any time suitable to them.

- E-teaching shall facilitate optimum utilization of ICT device by providing training to in-service teachers.
- E-teaching shall be the platform for transacting an e-curriculum

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